

TABLE 2
INFRA-RED SPECTRA

	Trans	Cis
$\nu(N_2)$ as	2050 (v.s.)	2015 (v.s.)
$\nu(N_2)$ S	1245 (s)	1260 (s), 1285 (s)
$\delta(N_2)$	650 (m)	610 (m)

The vibration of lattice water are generally found in the region (3550-3200) cm^{-1} corresponding to the symmetric and antisymmetric O-H stretching modes^{1,2}. In both these azido complexes strong bands appear in these regions viz. 3200, 3300 and 3400 cm^{-1} for trans and a very broad strong absorption band from 3100 to 3400 cm^{-1} for the cis. An absorption at 1670 (S) for trans and 1680 (S) for cis may be assigned to H-O-H bending mode^{1,2}.

The azide outside the co-ordinating sphere for both these compounds was precipitated with silver nitrate, the filtrate acidified with perchloric acid, and then irradiated. It is found that in contrast to azido complexes containing ammonia and ethylenediamine, these biguanide complexes are rather inert to irradiation with visible light in perchloric acid medium and undergo decomposition on prolonged irradiation with ultra-violet light (365 nm). The details of this photodecomposition are under investigation.

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Titrimetric Determination of Lead(II), Molybdate and Phosphate using Pyridinol-Azo-Dyes as Visual Indicators

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IN the present study pyridinol azo dyes 1-(2,3-dihydroxy-4-pyridylazo)-4-benzene sulphonic acid (DHP-4S) and 1-(5-chloro-4-pyridylazo-2,3-diol)-4-benzene sulphonic acid (CPD-4S) have been successfully used as indicators for the titrimetric determination of lead (II)(complexometrically) and molybdate, phosphate (volumetrically). Earlier, formation of these dyes have been used as a sensitive test for the detection and determination of nitrite¹. The dyes have also been utilised for the complexometric determination of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II)².

Experimental

Reagents

Standard lead(II), molybdate and phosphate solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of Analar $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Na}_2(\text{MoO}_4)$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and KH_2PO_4 respectively in double distilled water. 0.1% Dye solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Recommended Procedure

Determination of Lead(II) : To a suitable aliquot containing 10.35-414.4 mg of lead(II) add 5 ml of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer of suitable pH (Table 1) and 0.1-0.3 ml of 0.1% indicator solution (DHP-4S or CPD-4S). Dilute the solution to approximately 20 ml by adding doubly distilled water and titrate at room temperature (27°) against standard EDTA ($1 \times 10^{-1} M$) taken in a microburette till a sharp colour change (magenta or red to orange) is obtained (Table 1). A white precipitate formed during the titration disappears on shaking. Titrations in reverse order can also be performed but the buffer should be added a few millilitre before the end-point.

NOTES

TABLE 1

OPTIMUM CONDITIONS FOR THE TITRATION OF LEAD(II), MOLYBDATE AND PHOSPHATE

Variables	Titration of Lead (II)		Titration of molybdate		Titration of phosphate
	DHP-4S	GPD 4S	DHP-4S	GPD-4S	GPD-4S
Colour change at the end-point	Red to Orange	Magenta to Orange	Orange to Red	Orange to Magenta	Orange to Magenta
Temperature range	15-80°C	15-80°C	30-80°C	30-80°C	20-80°C
Indicator concentration 0.1% pH range, buffer	0.1-0.3 ml 8.0-10.0	0.1-0.3 ml 8.0-10.5	0.1-0.4 ml 5.5-7.0	0.1-0.4 ml 5.5-7.0	0.1-0.4 ml 5.5-7.0
Standard deviation	0.013	0.011	0.014	0.018	0.018
% Relative Error	0.17%	0.17%	0.25%	0.40%	0.40%
pH at which titrations performed	10.0	10.0	7.0	7.0	7.0

Determination of Molybdate and Phosphate: To a suitable aliquot containing 1.60-160.0 mg of molybdate or 0.95-76.0 mg of phosphate, add 5 ml of pyridine buffer of suitable pH (Table 1) and 0.1 to 0.4 ml of 0.1% indicator solution (Table 1). Dilute the solution to approximately 20 ml and titrate the contents at 30 with shaking, against standard Pb(NO₃)₂ (1 × 10⁻¹ M) until the end-point is reached. Reverse titrations have also been performed.

Titrations in presence of diverse ions

Interferences due to a large number of foreign ions have been studied by taking 82.88 mg of lead (II), 64.00 mg of molybdate or 28.50 mg of phosphate and following the recommended procedure as given above. Masking agents were also used to undo some of the interferences. The results of the studies are summarised below:

Titration of Lead(II)

Ions like F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, CH₃COO⁻, ClO₄⁻, BO₃³⁻, CNS⁻, thiourea, NO₂⁻, TI⁺ and Sr²⁺ do not interfere when present up to 5000 ppm level. However, PO₄³⁻ interferes even in traces. The following ions do not interfere (amounts in ppm). Masking agents, wherever used are given in brackets.

S²⁻(100-200), tartarate (100-200), citrate(200), Ti⁴⁺(120) Sb³⁺(122), MoO₄²⁻(24-48), Ge⁴⁺(100) (F⁻), WO₄²⁻(184), UO₂²⁺(240), La³⁺(70), In³⁺(23), Os⁸⁺(5) (CN⁻), V⁵⁺(25.5), Sn²⁺(25) (F⁻), Rh³⁺(4.1), Hg²⁺(5000) (CN⁻), Cu²⁺(5000) (CN⁻), Co²⁺(1000) (CN⁻), Ni²⁺(1500) (CN⁻), Zn²⁺(654) (CN⁻), Fe²⁺(280) (CN⁻) and Cd²⁺(112.4) (CN⁻).

Titration of Molybdate and Phosphate

Anions like CH₃COO⁻, ClO₄⁻, BO₃³⁻, CNS⁻, thiourea, NO₂⁻ and I⁻ do not interfere up to 5000 ppm level. However, F⁻, SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, S₂O₈²⁻, S₂O₃²⁻, S²⁻, C₄H₂O₆²⁻, citrate, C₂O₄²⁻, Cu²⁺ and Cd²⁺ interfere seriously in both the cases.

For molybdate the tolerance limits (in ppm) of various ions are given below. Masking agents, if used, are mentioned in parentheses.

Cl⁻(1000), Br⁻(1000), CN⁻(500), Ti⁴⁺(6), Sb³⁺

(30.5), Sr²⁺(11-22), Fe²⁺(5), WO₄²⁻(18.4-45), TI⁺(5.1), UO₂²⁺(136), La³⁺(7), Os⁸⁺(4.8), V⁵⁺(10), Sn²⁺(50-100), Rh³⁺(8.2) and Hg²⁺(10-20) (I⁻).

For phosphate the tolerance limits of various ions, with masking, given below:

Ti⁴⁺(12), Sb³⁺(30.5), Sr²⁺(4.5), Ge⁴⁺(10), WO₄²⁻(184), TI⁺(20.5), UO₂²⁺(68), La³⁺(14), In³⁺(46) Os⁸⁺(9.7), V⁵⁺(25.5), Sn²⁺(5), Rh³⁺(16.5), Hg²⁺(1000) (CN⁻), Co²⁺(15) (CN⁻), Ni²⁺(58) (CN⁻), Zn²⁺(65.4) (CN⁻) and Fe²⁺(5.6) (CN⁻).

Results and Discussion

Optimum conditions for the estimation of lead(II) molybdate and phosphate have been established and statistical evaluation of the results have been carried out (Table 1).

In molybdate titrations, lead to molybdate ratio at the equivalence point is 1 : 1 which corresponds to the formation of PbMoO₄ and in phosphate titrations the ratio of lead to phosphate in the precipitate is 5 : 3 corresponding to an apatite type phosphate³⁻·4 Pb₅(PO₄)₃OH.

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